

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRIMARY EDUCATION PROCESS

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Abstract. *It is important to emphasize the significance of the primary educational process in enhancing the efficiency of education. This includes prioritizing creative activities and creating ample opportunities for the development of students' minds, critical thinking, and personal growth. Additionally, it is essential to consider the various components of a child's educational activities and to begin evaluating the results of educational outcomes for third-grade students.*

Keywords: *process, evaluation, development, creativity, personality, professional competence, intellectual, spiritual and moral, socio-economic development, student, personality-oriented education, competence-based approach, level.*

Introduction.

It is known to everyone that primary education is presented as the initial stage of general secondary education in the educational system of New Uzbekistan. Definitely, modern primary education is an educational process based on scientific learning, the main goal of which is to develop children's basic reading, writing and counting skills, as well as to form their understanding of the objective world.

Obviously, for improving the effectiveness of the current primary education process, it must be improved and enriched with new approaches.

In the current conditions of the comprehensive development of the national personnel training system in our country, it is necessary to further improve it in order to ensure the quality and effectiveness of primary education. At present time primary education faces a number of tasks:

1. To develop in primary school students the desire and ability to read, learn and apply the knowledge they have acquired.
2. To strengthen the desire for high development of cognitive processes and cognitive activity in primary school students.

Certainly, the quality and effectiveness of the educational process will increase only when a conscious desire for cognitive activity is formed. If the primary education process does not instill in the student a desire for knowledge, his desire for knowledge will weaken as he moves to higher grades. This, in turn, negatively affects the level of knowledge, skills and competencies of primary school graduates.

Besides that, primary school students should also develop a sense of responsibility for monitoring and objectively evaluating the knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by them and their classmates. The student should be able to model the provided educational material. In this process, students should understand that not every drawing can become a model. For this, students should also have developed skills of imagination and hypotheses. In elementary grades,

the leading place is occupied by lessons aimed at reading and learning. In addition, games, sports and creative activities should play an important role in the development of primary school students. But educational activities should be aimed at a specific goal - the all-round development of the child, unlike all other activities. Including the development of oral and written literacy, protection of physical development and health of students. This developmental educational process creates ample opportunities for the development of the mind, thinking and personal growth of the student. The initial stage of personality development in this sense is primary education.

Discussion and Results

While developing the process of primary education, the professional competence and level of education of the teacher, child psychology, modern pedagogy of primary education and best practices in this area, the concept of personality-oriented education and competence-based approach are taken into account. Knowledge of the basics is important to ensure the quality and effectiveness of primary education.

One of the important conditions for the intellectual, spiritual, moral, socio-economic development of the individual in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the organization of the education system, especially primary education, based on the concept of personality-oriented education and competence-based approach. The development of the education system is the basis of social progress. This requires the systematic development of innovative technologies used in the primary education system, which will speed up the process of students acquiring competencies and adapting them to the requirements of a developing society. The growing need for quality education is becoming increasingly relevant as an important life value for the citizens of Uzbekistan. Because quality education is a key factor in socio-political stability and justice.

It is important that education be open to external needs, that the identification and manifestation of leaders be based on selection, that new approaches be successfully implemented in practice, that comprehensive solutions be targeted, and that decisions taken be holistic.

Specific areas of primary education organization based on a personality-oriented and competence-based approach should be implemented within the framework of national planning. The strategic goal of the educational policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to increase the availability of quality education taking into account the development needs of the individual and society.

The process of primary education should be organized, first of all, on the basis of the principle of humanism. Because the educational policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is distinguished by its humane nature. This policy is primarily aimed at being based on universal human values. The process of primary education, organized on the basis of the principle of humanity, should ensure the free development of students.

The content and essence of education are also changing in connection with the integration and globalization processes taking place throughout the world. That is why primary school teachers have a very important task - to form an independently thinking personality with the potential for self-awareness and a new intellectual level. Such students should have the opportunity to engage in theoretical thinking, engage in creative activities, and independently manage their actions and activities.

For achieving this, it is necessary to develop a high level of reading skills in primary school students. It is known that all children have unique talents. When we talk about the level of

giftedness of children, we mean children whose level of perception and creative thinking is higher than that of their peers.

If a first-grader is ready for learning and understands its necessity, he will develop the skills of creativity, thinking, searching for natural solutions, and his development as a person will be achieved as a result of enriching his intellectual sphere.

These days the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan places high demands on the primary education system. To meet these requirements, primary school teachers must be highly qualified and have real intelligence. A primary school teacher must instill modern knowledge and the basics of national education in students during the teaching process. In this process, he must, first of all, love and respect his students. Teachers must be able to identify the abilities of students entering primary school on the basis of the concept and determine the paths of their development. Because the abilities of students are a reflection of their success.

Currently, the question is "Under what circumstances should a child be admitted to school at the age of six?". The answer to this question is being sought. Readiness for school is related to the child's readiness to perceive the components of educational activity, in other words, readiness for school. In order to be accepted to school at the age of six, a child must have reached a certain level of development, be ready to participate in the cognitive process, have the ability to be emotionally receptive and be free to a certain extent. In addition, they must have developed certain personal qualities. It is advisable to check these qualities and the child's level of readiness for school using pedagogical and psychological tests with multiple-choice answers.

Moreover, the level of a child's functional readiness for school should be determined by the school psychological service (which must necessarily include a psychologist, pediatrician, speech therapist and primary school teacher). In this case, the school must conduct a comprehensive pedagogical and psychological diagnosis with teachers teaching 6-7 year old children with special needs.

However, school education, especially primary education, can only be effective when it is focused on the personality and development of the child. To ensure children's literacy, all students in one class must be mentally healthy. When conducting a comprehensive psychological and pedagogical diagnosis with children, the results of the examination must be thoroughly studied by teachers and a description of the child's mental development must be given. Children who are developing with developmental disabilities must be placed in remedial classes.

Only after a thorough study of the development, level of knowledge and upbringing of children and the identification of qualitative changes should they be given the opportunity to continue their education in the next class.

It is important to assess the learning outcomes of primary school students. However, both students and teachers need to know the accuracy of the grade given and what type of work it reflects.

Methodology for setting lesson goals and expected results

The goal is the most important factor in the teaching and learning processes, as well as in the educational process.

It is formed based on the goal and content of studying a specific subject or the content of educational influence and corresponds to the main content of this form of education. The goal determines the joint movement of the educator and the student to a common result. Therefore, we

need to formulate it carefully, that is, the goal should be so clear and specific that it is aimed at achieving the following:

- It is necessary to organize a didactic and educational process that guarantees the achievement of the set goal under certain conditions and within certain time frames;
- At the end of the learning process, specific conclusions can be made about the level of goal achievement.

Based on this, the goals of education are expressed through the learning outcomes, which are expressed in the actions of students.

Stages of educational process design

1. Setting learning objectives and corresponding expected results
2. Developing to control tasks and assessment criteria based on the results
3. Developing a technological map of the learning process (lesson plan)

Focus on setting objectives and expected results

- the level of students' mastery of the BKM on the planned topic;
- the main attention should be paid to the joint activity of the researcher with students to achieve the planned learning results.

The next most important component of lesson plan development is the expression of the expected result. The expected result reflects the effectiveness of the learning process and describes the degree of goal achievement. The learning and teaching process is effective only when the goal set corresponds to the expected result. Based on this, the stages of educational process design can be defined as follows:

Approximate list of verbs corresponding to the categories of learning objectives according to B. Bloom's taxonomy:

Knowledge	Restore, record, communicate, name, write, express, distinguish, identify, tell
Repeat	Understanding Prove, replace, clarify, define, explain, translate, change, describe, reveal
Apply	implement, calculate, demonstrate, use, teach, clarify, realize, solve
Analysis	Extract, separate, differentiate, classify, conclude, predict, place, divide, explore, group
Synthesis	Invent, generalize, combine, plan, develop, systematize, unite, create, compose, design
Diagnose	prove, measure, substantiate, assert, evaluate, check, control, compare, contrast

Expression of the lesson objective and its expected results

At present time it is common to plan learning objectives (expected results, tasks) in three directions (Figure 1). Learning objectives are a predetermination of the knowledge, skills and qualifications that a student should acquire, and the acquisition of new ones at the end of a certain educational process. This is considered a skill. If the lesson objectives are not clearly defined, then its content and didactic structure will depend to a certain extent on the case. Only when the lesson objectives are clear, can their content be determined and the lesson development from a didactic point of view can be started. Therefore, it is very important for each teacher and educator to have the skills of setting, correctly setting and selecting learning objectives in the educational process. The learning objectives of each lesson must be defined in advance. The identified learning

objectives determine which materials should be selected for the lesson content, which methodological and didactic materials should be used for its implementation. Thus, in any educational process, learning objectives determine the content, methods and means of teaching.

Educational (goals related to cognition, thinking) - these include goals from memorizing and recalling the studied material to solving problems, that is, educational goals set in the curriculum, manual and in the teacher's daily practice. Goals in this area is to answer the question: "What does the student think and know?". In this case, it is necessary to take into account the student's previous knowledge.

Developmental (practical goals) — goals related to the formation of certain types of activity. Goals in this area answer the question: "What can the student do?" Such goals include writing, speaking, drawing and graphic representation skills, as well as goals within the framework of physical education and labor training;

Upbringing (emotional values, feelings) goals include perception, interest, readiness for influence, assimilation of a value system and their active expression.

Subject area goals answer the question: "What will the student feel?" These are interests and inclinations that form attitudes, experience certain emotions and implement them in activities.

Expected results are specific, measurable learning outcomes in a particular subject or section.

The effectiveness of a lesson can be achieved by clearly formulating expected results. Therefore, when formulating them, it is necessary, along with the goals, to provide indicators for achieving the expected results, evaluation criteria, and a description of the conditions necessary to achieve these results. When determining expected results, the following requirements should be taken into account:

- it should be realistic;
- it should be clear;
- it should be limited in time;
- it should be measurable.

Development of expected learning outcomes is the most important step in the process of developing a lesson on a subject. Since shortcomings and mistakes made at this stage will negatively affect subsequent stages of lesson implementation. Therefore, in pedagogical technology, the teacher should pay special attention to defining learning goals and expected learning outcomes.

Verbs used to express expected learning outcomes are divided into the following groups:

Verbs for expressing goals with a general description: analyze, calculate, describe, demonstrate, know, interpret, use, evaluate, understand, change, apply, create.

Verbs for expressing goals of the creative (research) type: classify, transform, change, regroup, reconstruct, predict, question, reorganize, generalize, systematize, simplify.

Verbs for expressing goals in oral and written speech: distinguish, express in words, note, determine, conclude, emphasize, express, speak, read, divide into parts, tell, narrate.

Verbs for expressing goals in the sphere of interpersonal relations: enter into a dialogue, express an opinion, express agreement (disagreement), answer, express gratitude, praise (approve), provide assistance, invite, join, cooperate, participate.

Lesson planning based on pedagogical technology is carried out in the following order:

Case 1. The process of designing expected learning outcomes.

Case 2. Developing control assignments. The content of control assignments should correspond to the expected results and determine the teacher's goals, the structure and content of the lesson, the methods and means of conducting the lesson, the form and place of feedback.

Case 3. Developing the teacher's goals.

Case 4. Selecting the content of the lesson and developing its structure.

Case 5. Selecting the methods and means of teaching the lesson.

Case 6. Developing the form and place of feedback with students.

While defining the taxonomy of learning objectives, it is recommended to adhere to the following rules of pedagogical technology:

1) The learning conditions and students' learning actions during the learning process exactly correspond to the expected actions during the final assessment.

2) Give students the opportunity to practice performing actions that are similar to the final movement, but not equal to it.

3) Immediately announce the result of each action to students.

4) Positively reinforce the actions expected from the student and do not scold for incorrect actions.

While implementing the learning process based on pedagogical technologies, a number of principles proposed by B. Skinner can be applied. Including:

The principle of steps. Based on this principle, the educational material should be divided into as small parts as possible.

The principle of immediate confirmation of the answer. The student should be able to obtain information about the correct answer (solution). To do this, the student must compare his answer with the standard of the correct answer;

The principle of individualization of the pace of learning. Based on this principle, it is recommended to develop a system of tasks taking into account the individual characteristics of each student.

The tendency is to gradually increase the complexity of tasks. Learning tasks should move from simple to complex, and as soon as the student has achieved one goal, he should move on to another.

Reinforce knowledge in different ways: repeat the generalization of each stage of learning several times in different situations corresponding to the content, and demonstrate it with a sufficient number of carefully selected examples.

When a teacher wants to organize work on studying a certain topic, which didactic group of lessons should he choose? How much information should be covered in each lesson? What feedback mechanisms should be used and at what stage of the lesson? A number of questions arise: "Which methods are more effective?"

According to the leading scientists S.V. Ivanov, V.A. Onishchenko, the typologies of lessons studied by the students were introductory lessons, introductory classes with material; lessons on the formation of concepts, laws and rules; lessons on the application of knowledge in practice, skills lessons; repetition and generalization lessons; supervision lessons, mixed or combined lessons; lessons on obtaining new knowledge, lessons on mastering new skills and qualifications, lessons on the integrated application of knowledge, lessons on systematization and generalization of knowledge, a lesson on checking, assessing and adjusting knowledge, skills and abilities, a lesson on general analysis of the topic and the methods of its study, combined seminar

sessions, lessons on systematization and generalization of knowledge, lessons on interdisciplinary generalization of material, which were distinguished such types of lessons as lectures and practical classes.

Conclusion. Regardless of the type of lesson used, if the learning objectives are formulated correctly and pedagogical technologies are used adequately, such lessons will certainly be effective. Society and its social development are the subject of historical science. The subject of this discipline is events that occurred in the past, and their scientific, objective study and teaching to students, as well as the teaching of history in general, are currently determined at the level of state policy. The role and importance of history in the formation of the social consciousness of students today is greater than ever before. Therefore, teachers of this subject should pay special attention to the organization of lessons taking into account modern requirements. Designing the lesson process is important in the implementation of state educational standards for teaching history. While developing a lesson, it is necessary to choose the right teaching methods, that is, to ensure that the goals and content of the lesson correspond to the capabilities of the teacher and students.

While developing a lesson plan, the teacher must consistently and comprehensively complete the following tasks.

Step 1: The teacher must be familiarized with the curriculum, textbook, teaching aid and general characteristics of the class.

Step 2: Define the main objectives of the lesson: educational, training, developmental.

Step 3: Organize the main stages of the lesson correctly, clearly and consistently.

Step 4: Identify the main points of the content of each stage of the lesson.

Step 5: Select teaching methods, tools and technologies for each part of the lesson.

Step 6: Guide the teaching of each part of the lesson; Choose lesson formats for the whole class, small groups or individually.

Step 7: Choose differentiated exercises and tasks for students who learn slowly and have good preparation.

Step 8: Choose the appropriate amount of homework in accordance with the time constraints of the students of the corresponding class.

It is recommended to use the Karpalak technology for studying this stage. The next stage of studying the topic involves analyzing the questions on this topic. At this stage, each student must complete a task in writing and justify their opinion. In this case, the ThRRG technology (thought, reason, reasoning, generalization) is used. Thus, the application of methods and technologies throughout the lesson occurred in the following sequence:

-Wheelbarrow method.

-ThRRG technology.

Certainly, this sequence should be implemented as a whole in the process of studying the topic, and for each part of the topic, along with the selection of methods, means and technologies, the forms of training (group, individual) were determined.

The next task in drawing up a lesson plan is the selection of differentiated exercises and tasks for students with slow learning and strong preparation. The tasks to be completed should move from simple to complex.

The content of the homework should be included at the end of the lesson plan. Homework is assigned based on the above topic, while it should be taken into account that the homework should be a logical continuation of the material covered in the lesson.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that while working on a lesson plan, it is necessary to clearly formulate the educational goals and results that must be achieved so that the developed lessons guarantee the quality of knowledge.

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